

TRIGONOMETRIC INEQUALITIES THAT ARE REDUCED TO ALGEBRAIC FORM WITH RESPECT TO FUNCTIONS AND THEIR SOLUTION.

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ABSTRACT

*Solving trigonometric inequalities ultimately leads to
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1. Solving trigonometric inequalities ultimately leads to solving simple trigonometric inequalities. they lead to solving the familiar trigonometric inequalities of the forms

$$\sin x > a, \quad \cos x < a, \quad \operatorname{tg} x < a. \quad (1)$$

Formulas for finding solutions to commonly used simple trigonometric equations:

Equation	Solution	Equation	Solution
$\sin x = 0$	$x = \pi n, \quad n$	$\cos x = 0$	$x = \frac{\pi}{2} + \pi n, \quad n$
$\sin x = 1$	$x = \frac{\pi}{2} + 2\pi n, \quad n$	$\cos x = 1$	$x = 2\pi n, \quad n$
$\sin x = -1$	$x = -\frac{\pi}{2} + 2\pi n, \quad n$	$\cos x = -1$	$x = (2n + 1)\pi, \quad n$

2. Now we consider the inequality

$$a \sin^2 x + b \sin x + c > 0, \quad a > 0. \quad (2)$$

as follows. Inequality (2) leads to

$$at^2 + bt + c > 0. \quad (3)$$

by marking $\sin x = t$. Let's $D = b^2 - 4ac < 0$; inequality (3), where $a > 0$, has infinitely many solutions, however inequality (3), which $a < 0$ has not any solutions. For $a > 0$ the inequality (3) is satisfied for any t . From that, we can say the inequality is satisfied for any $\sin x$ or for any x .

Let's $D \geq 0$, in there, the inequality (3) has the nulls in the forms

$$t_1 = \frac{-b + \sqrt{D}}{2a}, \quad t_2 = \frac{-b - \sqrt{D}}{2a}, \quad (4)$$

If, their absolute value is less than 1, the solution form is $t \in (-1; t_1) \cup (t_2; +1)$, and the inequality (2) leads in the form

$$\sin x \in (-1; t_1) \cup (t_2; +1).$$

Let's, look the case, which one of the nulls t_1, t_2 of the inequality (2) is more than one:

If, the nulls are $|t_1| > 1, t_2 > 1 (t_2 < -1)$, then, when we write the solution to inequality (2), we know that one of the multipliers is a definite negative (positive) number. According to the property of inequalities, we can ignore the multiplier (a negative multiplier) by changing the inequality sign (in positive one unchanged the inequality sign) respectively. Then we will solve the part with unclear signs.

We look some examples with the their solutions

Example 1. Solve inequality $\cos 2x - \frac{\pi}{4} > -\frac{1}{2}$.

Solution: by using formula we can write

$$2x - \frac{\pi}{4} - \arccos \left(-\frac{1}{2} + 2\pi n \right); \arccos \left(-\frac{1}{2} + 2\pi n \right) ,$$

there is $\arccos \left(-\frac{1}{2} \right) = \frac{2\pi}{3}$, then we bring

$$2x - \frac{2\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4} + 2\pi n; \frac{2\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{4} + 2\pi n , \text{ the we find the solution}$$

$$x - \frac{5\pi}{24} + \pi n; \frac{11\pi}{24} + \pi n , n \in \mathbf{Z} .$$

Example 2. Solve the inequality $\sin(x^2) \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$.

Solution: According to the formula

$$x^2 \in \left[-\pi - \arcsin \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + 2\pi n; \arcsin \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + 2\pi n \right] .$$

In this case, from the definition domain of x , we can write

$$x^2 \in \left[0; \frac{\pi}{4} \right] \cup \left[\frac{3\pi}{4} + 2\pi n; \frac{5\pi}{4} + 2\pi n \right]$$

from this

$$x_1 \in \left[0; \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \right] \cup \left[\sqrt{\frac{3\pi}{4} + 2\pi n}; \sqrt{\frac{5\pi}{4} + 2\pi n} \right]$$

and

$$x_2 \in \left[-\sqrt{\frac{5\pi}{4} + 2\pi n}; -\sqrt{\frac{3\pi}{4} + 2\pi n} \right] \cup \left[-\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}; 0 \right] .$$

If we add the intervals of these solutions, then the solution to the inequality is

$$x \in \left[-\sqrt{\frac{5\pi}{4} + 2\pi n}; -\sqrt{\frac{3\pi}{4} + 2\pi n} \right] \cup \left[-\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}; \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \right] \cup \left[\sqrt{\frac{3\pi}{4} + 2\pi n}; \sqrt{\frac{5\pi}{4} + 2\pi n} \right]$$

due to the fact that it must be not negative, n may bring only the volume 1, 2,

Example 3. Solve the inequality $2\sin^2 x - \sin x - 3 < 0$.

Solution: Through the representation $\sin x = t$, we obtain the quadratic inequality $2t^2 - t - 3 < 0$. The nulls of this inequality are $t_1 = -1$, $t_2 = \frac{3}{2}$. Then, in the reason of $2(t+1)(t-\frac{3}{2}) < 0$, the given inequality leads to the form $2(\sin x + 1)(\sin x - \frac{3}{2}) < 0$, from this it follows that the inequality holds for any values other than $\sin x = -1$, that is, the set of solutions of the inequality is $x = -\frac{\pi}{2} + 2\pi n, n \in \mathbf{Z}$.

Example 4. Solve inequality $2\sin^2 x - \cos x - 1 > 0$.

Solution: Let's $t = \cos x$, as well as $\sin^2 x = 1 - t^2$ and from that the inequality obtain the form

$$2(1-t^2) - t - 1 > 0 \text{ or } 2t^2 + t - 1 < 0.$$

To solve the inequality we can find the nulls $t_1 = -1$, $t_2 = \frac{1}{2}$ of the given inequality, then we obtain the inequality $2(t+1)(t-\frac{1}{2}) < 0$. According to the condition of the inequality, $\cos x = -1$ and from this $x = \pi + 2\pi n$, however and the solution of the remaining inequality $\cos x < \frac{1}{2}$ will be enough, that is $x = \frac{\pi}{3} + 2\pi n; \frac{5\pi}{3} + 2\pi n, n \in \mathbf{Z}$, the set of points $x = \pi + 2\pi n$ is situated in this interval, therefore, the solution to the inequality will be $x = \frac{\pi}{3} + 2\pi n; \pi + 2\pi n, \pi + 2\pi n; \frac{5\pi}{3} + 2\pi n, n \in \mathbf{Z}$.

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